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An Unknown Historian, Rajendralal Mitra

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Abstract

As the started Asiatic Society in 1784, 18th century, the historical method, as to be new trends. Mainly at first, british civilians have to be inspired this society. Based on the Asiatic Society, the original historiography was continued. Various books, Journals had been written by many authors and also conducted survey. Although, at first, native men were absent. But 2nd half of 19th century, they participated various sites. Raja Rajendralal Mitra, as, a big orient historian, who was not only had various journals and books, but also various essays. He became first native principle who presided that in Asiatic society. Although, before, he joined in this society. Various articles, journals, books had been published by him and later, glorious foreign universities have been invited him and speched there, in historical method. Beside, history, he also inspired politics, society, economy that as significant. Most enormous intellectual personality, Rajendralal Mitra, inspired to the Upanishad as, and, Dharmashastra's, historical method from early years to be attractive for him.

Keywords: *Asiatic Society, William Jones, Haraprasad Shastri, Nationalist, Upanishad, Rabindranath Tagore.*

Introduction:

In India, historically, in 1784, the Asiatic Society founded by William Jones. William Jones, as the president this society. He, researched, that, Aryan civilization, who native or foreigner. On the other hand, the language culture of Aryan, mixed various languages such as 'Latin', 'Celtic', 'Gothic', etc, had been shown, by him. To found that Asiatic Society, the native land what as, known and this society, participated, glorious pioneering nationalist historians, Rajendralal, Mitra, played, a crucial role in this Society for his researchable methodology.

Rajendralal Mitra born in 24 Pargana, on 16 Feb, in. 1822 and he born very rich family. He was grandson of Kalidas Maitra. His family lived in Hooghly district in konnagar. Later, they came to Calcutta and they lived near Mechuabazar. Later, they lived in Belegkata. His father name was Janmenjoy Mitra. He had 3 sons. Rajendralal was third son and was a sister. He early ages captured Bengali and Persi language, and later, he read Baidyanath Roy's 'Pathshala's home. Next times, he read Khem Basu's english pathsala. In, early childhood life, he was very intelligent boy. In 1838, he had in malaria diseases, some days. In 1839,

he married with Saudamani Devi who was Dharmdas Dutta's, 3rd daughter.

In 1846, on 5th Nov, with the fees of 500 rupees, he joined a post of assistant secretary and Librarian in Asiatic Society of Bengal. Now, a new era has been starting by him, because, he had many historians, and many glorious persons. He worked for Asiatic Society for 10 years. Various research articles were published into journal Sanskrit books had been edited and the edited works, today, known to as 'Bibliotheca Indica'. His, first edited Sanskrit works, as, Nitisara, by, Kamandaka. ¹ Ranjendralal who was 'Director of words', during the times of 1850-80. Next of time, he was to be the president of Asiatic Society of Bengal, in, 1885. He also edited numerous newspaper or journals, such as 'Hindoo Patriot' etc. Nirmal Sinha, praised to him and wrote, "Ranjendralal was very patriotic in his support of all efforts to promote the improvement of Bengali language. As a member of paper committee together with Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar, Rajnarayan Basu and others, he helped the selection of useful and instructive articles for the publication in the 'Tattwabodhini Patrika'". ²

Review of Existing Literature:-

Kaviguru, Rabindranath Tagore, in his, own work, 'My Reminiscences', "Dr. Rajendralal Mitra was not only profound scholar, but he had likewise a striking personality which shone through his features. Full of fire as he was in his public life, he could also unbend graciously so as to talk on the most difficult subjects to a stripling like myself without any trace of a tone". ³ A magazine, 'Bibidhertha Samgraha' that, was, as published between year of 1857-59, and later it's name, as, 'Rahasya Sandherba'. Dr. Indranil Sanayal, pointed out that he took LLD degree from Calcutta University in 1878 and later, in 1878, 'CIE' or 'Companionship of the Indian Empire' was taken. With the title of Raja, had been crucial role, in 1888 that he had. He was German Oriental Societies' fellow in 1864

and in Great Britain, Royal Asiatic Society of London gave a fellowship. Hungary and USA also selected him for fellowship. ⁴ Haraprasad Shastri, remarked for him that he was intellect person, for the criticism of the history and numerous articles. ⁵ He also talent historians and, writing skill was good.

Beside the newspaper of 'Hindoo Patriot', various kinds of journals also to be edited by him. ⁶ Prbhaschandra Dhar, thought, in 19th century was glorious era. Besides Rammohan; Vidyasagar, he was an intellect man whose interest was various subjects. ⁷ Arupratan Bhattacharya, shown that in 1891, on, 26 July, when he died, A.W.Croft, said "for wherever learning is cultivated there. The name of Rajendralal Mitra is held in honour,"⁸

Research objectives :-

1. To discuss, that, what was the role of Babu Rajendarlal Mitra?
2. To discuss that his research how to be predictable?
3. What was the role of Rajendralal's Antiquities of Orissa?

Works of Sir, Mitra:-

He published various articles in various Journals and newspapers. On the other hand, he, had various languages such as, English, Bengali, Sanskrit, Hindi, Oria, and Urdu. To conduct of the ancient Oriya history, he, visited these sites, with photographers. He published, in his own book 'Bharatiya Arya' which discuss that detail information from ancient era to medieval history and also many palm leaves were editing. ⁹ He served many manuscripts during the time of 1870-88. He also published that a manuscript in 1878 which, as, 'Buddha Gaya - The Hermitage of Sakya Muni' and also 57 plates and glorious photograph for the monuments were made by him, with the help of his grandson, Dilip Kumar Mitra. ¹⁰

On sculpture history, he played a crucial role. His glorious work as 'Antiquities of Orissa' based on detail account for the specific history of Orissa. Next he also published that Indo-Aryans (1881). Later, he also published new volume, with the contents of twenty-one. He also detail criticized against historian James Ferguson. Various articles also published by him into English languages. The Canary Review of The Asiatic Society had been gave a list. It, as, a journal of Royal Asiatic Society London. On the other hand, other articles, were -

1. Transactions of the Anthropological, society of London.
2. Journal of the Photographic Society of Bengal. ¹¹

He also various 'Upanishadas' translated into English language.

Other Activities of Raja Rajendralal Mitra:-

Besides, historian, he played crucial role in society. In 1863-76, he was 'Justice of Peace'. As, the new act, going to be run, in the year of 1876, he elected, member of Calcutta municipality. He had to develop, Calcutta city. ¹² For the vernal education, by him, played a crucial role. On 27 Feb in 1868, the British Indian Association, as member. On 7 may, in 1884 he speech in British Indian Association's meeting, that as—

"Thirty-two long years have elapsed since the establishment of this Association, and I have been connected with it nearly the whole time with the exception perhaps two months or three ". ¹³

Conclusion:-

In 19th century Raja Rammohan Roy, Vidyasagar made to develop Society, Rajendralal, who, as the other name of various kinds of activities. For the effect of British government, as the various kinds western education when founded, then, Oriental historiography

took a large part, Rajendralal made to criticism for the western theory. He took traditional method in his journals. In India, he discuss vivid account and Journals and to be published. London, Hungery, Germany also gave him fellow. He had to be thought of Permanent settlement. Politics, society vernacular education did not believe for him, that as very significant.

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